

Female Existence: A Brief Study of Alice Walker's The Color Purple

Mrs. Sanjivani Kharat* & Dr. Savita M. Signare**

Author Affiliation:

*Research Scholar, Department of English, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad. (M.S). India. Email: sanjivanikharat2@gmail.com

**Research Guide, Department of English, Siddharth Arts, Commerce & Science College, Jafrabad, Jalna. (M.S). India.

Citation of Article: Kharat, S. K., & Signare, S. M. (2024). Female Existence: A Brief Study of Alice Walker's The Color Purple International Journal of Classified Research Techniques & Advances (IJCRTA) ISSN: 2583-1801, 4(1), pg. 1-3. ijcrta.org

Abstract:

This research article is Female Existence A Brief Study of Alice Walker's The Color Purple, Alice Walker is an American novelist, Short story writer, Poet, and social activist in 1982 she became the first African American woman to win the Pulitzer Prize for Fiction, which she was awarded for her novel—The Color Purple. The paper aims to bring out the trials and troubles faced by women characters in the novel—The Color Purple by Alice Walker. Women urge a form of existence. The Color Purple has the theme of sexist oppression, patriarchal supremacy, and oppression of Black women Class struggles, and the status of Afro-American women. This paper's presentation focuses on female existence in the novel The Color Purple this also focuses on the different aspects of suffering the women undergo affected by various relationships.

Keywords: Existence, Oppression, Patriarchal Supremacy,

Introduction:

Alice Walker was born on (Feb 9, 1944) Alice Walker is especially known for novels, poems, and short stories that offer great insight into African American culture and often focus on women for the novel The Color Purple (1982), She became the first African American woman to win the Pulitzer Prize for fiction.

Alice Walker in The Color Purple reflects some true life struggles some of which she experienced directly and others that she heard were experienced by others. Alice Walker emphasized through their writing on community, portrayed the powers and struggles of Women in male-dominated society and thus developed a new and unique National anesthetic in literature.

Female Existence in Alice Walker's the Color Purple:

The Color Purple is a 1982 epistolary novel by American author Alice Walker which won the 1983 Pulitzer Prize for fiction and the National Book Award for Fiction In The Color Purple Walker shows the adverse impacts that the oppression of black women has on their development Black women suffer from discrimination and oppression from black men and the white men and women. Female characters such as Celie, Shug, Nettie's, and Sofia in The Color Purple are

dominated both psychologically and physically. The character of Celie the downtrodden, abused, despised is transformed into an Independent and Liberated woman at the end of the novel. She was dispersed and exploited because of her ugliness. This paper deals with the theme of the quest for self new identity and freedom to assert their marriage life. African American woman writers are attempting to define their existence and to sustain their self.

Celie quoted " I 'm poor, I'm black, I may be Ugly and can't cook (...) But I'm here" This line of Celie Shows the oppression of women by males culminated in society women like Celie were expected to marry, raise children, and run the household without receiving support from their male counterparts.

In the novel also highlights women showing the complete antithesis of Celie's characteristics. The revolutionary figure Shug Avery is introduced early in the novel and portrays all aspects of Independencies as defined by Virginia Woolf unlike Celie. Shug Avery works as a singer and earns money giving her sought-after economic independence. This allows for her to live out of wedlock which in turn gives her social independence. Shug Avery can freely express herself in a more outspoken manner without any restraints. Shug's attitude indicates the reality of Independence amongst females during the 1910s. However, being Independent comes at a great cost for Shug Avery she is routinely judged and disliked by many. This adds a layer to the hardships women had to face in terms of becoming autonomous.

In the novel, black feminism is unsuccessful at first because women are unaware of the existence of their problems. They suffer in silence as each one of them feels that the problems are unique to their lives for example; Celie is reluctant to report Pa even as he rapes her repeatedly for the fear of losing her mother (Horus 1986) instead of confining in another person in the society. She prefers to suffer in silence.

When Nettie comes out of her home and seeks help from Celie, Celie could not help instead Nettie leaves the house saying she will come back. Here Celie wants to survive in this world. So, she never voice out about the physical pain and harassment she undergoes in her life. After meeting Shug Avery, Celie understands herself and her identity in this world.

"I remember one time you said your life made you feel so ashamed you couldn't even talk it to sod, you had to write it, bad as you thought your writing was well, now I know what you mean," (the color purple 113) Experiencing loneliness, pain, and rejection from her family and outside Celie becomes spiritual and finds refuge from God. But continuous harassment she used to make her weak physically and mentally which led her to stop writing letters to God. But to the constants of Celie's character Sofia, a bold and strong woman character in the novel. Towards the end of the novel, Celie understands herself and love. She understands the completeness of life. She also understands that power, position, education money, or beauty will never make one valuable in this world, all her suffering was answered at last. Her achievement is Priceless which she attains with the help of many powerful persons. When she gets the letter from Shug that she going to come back home Celie is happy and contented and faces the world differently. Celie Crosse's three stages in her life that is first understand that if she loved something. She has to set it free second she thinks in a different way and third Nettie's moving tributes towards the fabulous African culture.

In the end, her love was understood by everyone, especially by her husband. Her dreams come true and she sets herself free from all the troubles and comes out with great strength and power.

Conclusion:

Alice Walker focuses mostly on black women who reside in a larger world and aim to achieve Independence and identity beyond male domination. Her character's strength resides in her acknowledgment debt to their relationship with men regard them as less significant than themselves merely because they are women. Walker throws a limelight upon the slavery male oppression and other things in this novel. Walker also portrayed women, characters who crave freedom from a brutally complex system of oppression that shapes their lives and their interpersonal relationships. Lastly, Walker brings out the voice of the voiceless through the protagonist Celie among the Society.

References:

- 1) Donnelly Mary, Alice Walker. *The Color Purple and Other Works*. Marshall Cavendish Benchmarks, 2009.
- 2) Seaman Donna *A conversation with Alice Walker* 2013.
- 3) Walker Alice, *The Color Purple*. Orion Books Ltd, 2007.

